

1 **NLR4 activation in the hematopoietic system of humans with autoimmune and inflammatory**
2 **disease.**

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7 We describe here activation of NLR4 in human autoimmune and inflammatory disease. In the whole
8 blood of humans with inflammatory bowel disease - Crohn's Disease and in ulcerative colitis - and in the
9 CNS of inflammatory disease, multiple sclerosis, NLR4 induction was a signature transcriptional feature
10 of the whole blood. We recently defined NLR4 as an inhibitor of the interferon system, together
11 complicating understanding of NLR4 as an inflammatory mediator, through NLR4-induced factors
12 outside of the interferon pathway, as opposed to a compensatory change in innate immune signaling to
13 help resolve physiologically harmful levels of immune activation. NLR4 was co-regulated closely with
14 NLR family members NLRP7 and NLRP12. Consistent with an inflammatory role for NLRP12, *NLRP12*
15 activation was observed in the whole blood in CD, UC, and in MS. NLR4 activation in the context of
16 NLRP12 induction was concomitant with increased expression of TNF family effectors TNFSF13,
17 TNFSF14, TNFRSF14 and the type II TNF receptor TNFRSF1b. NLR4 was closely co-regulated with
18 TNFSF14 (LIGHT), and the tissues of LIGHT transgenic mice displayed activation of *NLRP12*. The data
19 reveal activation of the interferon-inhibiting NLR family member NLR4 in the hematopoietic system in
20 autoimmune and inflammatory disease and indicate contributions of NLRP12 and NLRP7 to a
21 transcriptional program marked by TNFSF13 and TNFSF14 expression.
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